

MODEL FOR TEACHING CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

¹Rasulova Nilufar, ²Makhmudova Maftuna, ³Shorustamova Mokhira

¹Associate Professor of the Department of Public Health and Health Care, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

²5 th year pediatric faculty student, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

³3 th year pediatric faculty student, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the analysis of scientific work, which describes a five-step model of training and the development of social skills in children with autism spectrum disorders, using a very popular method of video modeling.*

Keywords: *children with disorders, technologies, video modeling, development of social skills, assessment of social interaction.*

Today, there are a large number of children with autism spectrum disorders with insufficient development of social skills. In our country, the attention of specialists to the problem of autism has been drawn since the late 60s. Initially, the study was carried out by child psychiatrists (Ivanov E. S., Demyanchuk L. N., Demyanchuk R. V., A. E. Zelenetskaya, D. N. Isaev, O. P. Yuryeva, V. M. Bashina, V. E. Kagan, K. S. Lebedinskaya) [1]. They considered autism within the framework of childhood schizophrenia or schizoid (autistic) psychopathy (T. P. Simson, G. E. Sukhareva, M. O. Gurevich) [6]. One of the scientists who has been working on this problem for more than one or two years is Scott Bellini, who wrote an article in which he describes a five - step model of communication training, while all attention is paid to the help method, which has become very popular and relatively new, but is already actively used in practice – video modeling. One of the main features of autism in both children and adults is a disorder of social functioning, which leads to a number of problems, such as failure in school, rejection from peers and failures in communicating with people, depression, anxiety and other negative consequences. Many children with autism are willing and eager to communicate, but unfortunately they often lack the social skills to communicate successfully. When children with autism describe their anxiety, it is similar to performing on stage: trembling, rapid heartbeat, trouble concentrating). Moreover, the excitement is caused in the child not only by performing in front of an audience, but even the very thought of performing is already stressful. Many of us try to avoid such situations-this is a typical way to protect ourselves from stress. A for children with autism spectrum disorders it is also typical to avoid any social situations due to a lack of social skills, so the child does not have the opportunity to acquire them. In his article, Scott Bellini describes a five-step model of communication training, which looks like this [4]: 1. Assessment of social interaction. 2. Distinguishing between lack of skill acquisition and lack of application. 3. Choosing an intervention strategy. 4. Performing the intervention. 5. Evaluate and track progress. Children with autism spectrum disorders are more likely to communicate with adults than with their peers, as adults simplify this task for children – they do all the "work" on communication for the child [4]. The lack of skill acquisition/lack of skill use model helps us choose intervention strategies that are appropriate for the current lack. This is the advantage of this stage. The most important thing is that the strategies used correspond to the child's personal needs, and there is a logical explanation

for the method used. It is very important to constantly encourage your child for every little effort and participation in the training program. When choosing a correction method, it is necessary to take into account the principle: change the environment or behavior of the child. For example, teaching peer helpers to interact with the child during the day at school, training about autism for classmates, including the child in various leisure groups (sports teams, scout groups) [2]. On the other hand, if you do not change the environment, but work on the child's behavior, then organize such training for him that will allow him to be successful in communication. The main thing is not to focus on one thing, otherwise you can fail. It is necessary to make efforts both in changing the child's environment and in working on his behavior, this will ensure self-confidence and the acquired skill will be met with understanding by peers [5]. To date, there is a whole list of methods of teaching children social skills that have proven effective in teaching children with autism. For example, engaging peers as helpers who interact with a child with ASD throughout the day. They must have social and play skills, attend school regularly, and have early experience with children with autism. They are instructed about autism behaviors in a polite and age-appropriate way. This method helps to generalize new skills in the natural environment. Another good example of learning social skills is the role-playing/behavioral rehearsal method. It involves replaying various situations or activities in order to put into practice the acquired skills or those that the child had difficulty applying. Role-playing games can be scripted or spontaneous. In the course of training, the speed of performing actions and self-confidence will increase [3]. And finally, one of the most effective methods of teaching social skills – video modeling. Adults, peers, and the child can participate in it. Video modeling is viewing a demonstration of some behavior on video and then repeating the behavior of the model. The advantage of video modeling is that it becomes a visual confirmation of the child's own success! Scott Bellini conducted an analysis of video modeling studies, including 20 works by his colleagues, in which 63 children with autism participated. The results confirm that video modeling is an effective intervention method for social-and communication skills in children and adolescents with autism. These techniques persist over time and carry over to other people and situations. Studies have shown a dramatic increase in behavior during the average duration of the intervention (viewing 9 videos lasting three minutes) [5]. Thus, an analysis of the psychological and pedagogical literature on the problem of insufficient development of social skills in children with autism spectrum disorders has shown that the use of video modeling technology contributes to: teaching children with ASD a wide range of social skills, from the simplest to professional (showing initiative and addressing others); reducing unwanted (interfering) behavior of the child; consolidating the simulated behavior of the child adult-guided behaviors; students with autism can act more independently and best match their typically developing peers.

REFERENCES

1. Bashina V. M. Autism in childhood, Moscow, 2019, P-212.212.
2. Ivanov E. S., Demyanchuk L. N., Demyanchuk R. V. Detsky autism: diagnostics and correction. - SPb., 2014. - C P. 80
3. Nesterova A. A., Aisina R. M., Suslova T. F. Model of support for positive socialization of children with autistic spectrum disorders (ASD): complex and interdisciplinary approaches part 1. Foreign models of teaching social skills to children with ASD / A. A. Nesterova, R. M. Aisina, T. F. Suslova // Education and Science. 2016, No. 2, pp. 145-155.

4. Simson, T. P. Psychology of abnormal child development: a textbook : in 2 volumes / Ed. by V. V. Lebedinsky, M. K. Bardyshevskaya. Moscow: CHERO : Moscow University Press: Vysshaya shkola Publ., 2002, pp. 394-412. 5. Scott Bellini. Building social relationships: a systematic approach to teaching social interaction skills to children and adolescents with autism and other social difficulties. - Ed.: AAPK textbooks (November 12, 2017) - C P. 315.